

Study of Pandawa Characters in Mahabharata's Story Learned With Indonesian Character Education

Muhammad Arifin¹; Arif Rahman Hakim²

Faculty of Math and Science Indraprasta PGRI University Jakarta, Indonesia

E-Mail: dutabudayaindraprasta@gmail.com

Submitted : May 7, 2021

Revised : May 20, 2021

Published : May 31, 2021

Abstract: Wayang has been recognized by UNESCO as a Masterpiece of Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity. However, in reality, there are facts among the younger generation of Indonesians who are still low on an understanding of wayang culture, especially in the Mahabharata story. Specifically, it is often found that the young generation in formal education circles understands the character of the Pandawa characters in the Mahabharata story. On the other hand, the younger generation of Indonesia is also being encouraged to have a character that is following the character education program of the Indonesian nation. This article, which is compiled in the form of a literature review, aims to examine the character of the Pandawa figures in the Mahabharata story to be aligned with the character education of the Indonesian nation in the formal education environment. The conceptual substance of this article is in the form of an effort to optimize character education through understanding the Pandawa characters in the Mahabharata story so that it can form the younger generation as human resources who have superior competencies as well as holistic characteristics as a manifestation of building the civilization of the life of the nation and state of Indonesia.

Keywords: Mahabharata Story, Pandawa Character, Indonesian Nation Character Education.

1. Introduction

Wayang has been recognized by UNESCO since 2003 as a Masterpiece of Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity. This should be something to be proud of for all Indonesian people because one of the national cultures of the Indonesian nation is recognized by UNESCO. Riyanto (2011) explains "When Ki Hajar Dewantara stated that national culture is a collection of the peaks of regional culture, one of the peaks must be the art of wayang performance." Wayang as one of the cultural products of the land of Java can certainly become an important icon for the representation of Indonesia's national cultural expressions. It is also very natural when wayang is used as the most important icon of the development of Indonesian national culture in various fields including in the field of education. With that sense of pride, formal education should be able to make wayang the main weapon of conveying learning messages. But in reality, there is still relatively minimal formal education in the modern era which makes wayang the main weapon in conveying learning messages.

There are facts among the younger generation of Indonesians who are still low on an understanding of wayang culture, especially in the Mahabharata story. Hasani (2013: 110) states that "wayang is something foreign to students". The development of western

entertainment that has come to Indonesia has kept the younger generation away from traditional arts, one of which is wayang. The younger generation prefers entertainment in the form of music concerts, films, and games, which are supported by sophisticated technology. Haryadi, Irfansyah, & Santosa (2013) explain that "the occurrence of modernization which is marked by the advancement of technology and the entry of western culture into Indonesia has caused Wayang Kulit to begin to be abandoned by the community, especially young people". It cannot be denied that the facts on the ground show that films, music concerts, and games are preferred over wayang which is considered ancient and does not follow the times in the present era. If this is left unchecked, the sense of pride among the younger generation of Indonesians will gradually fade over the wayang culture as a Masterpiece of Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity.

In general, the essence of education includes learning and teaching interactions. It cannot be denied that education can be used as a bridge for cultural transformation from one generation to the next. Because education in Indonesia has three channels, namely formal, non-formal, and informal channels, it is only fitting that wayang be performed informal education. Various things related to wayang in Indonesia have become material for stories that must be preserved from generation to generation so that the relay stick of cross-generational cultural transformation is well preserved. In-Law No.20 of 2003, it is stated that: "Learning is a process of interaction between students and educators and learning resources in a learning environment". In this case, it can be understood that learning resources, teachers, and students become a unity, there must be good interaction with each other. The Character Education Strengthening Program (PPK) was initiated by the Ministry of Education and Culture in line with the efforts to make the National Movement for the Mental Revolution (GNRM) succeed. In this case, the priority institution is basic education, starting from the level of Formal and Non-formal Early Childhood Education, Elementary School equivalent, then Junior High School equivalent, to later Senior High School equivalent.

Various ways can be done to convey learning messages in the formal education pathway, including by bringing the puppet culture to the learning classroom. This of course can automatically foster a variety of good characters in the younger generation, especially students in classrooms. Because it can be believed that the character development or culture of a nation can never be separated from the various traditional values that underlie and raise it. The birth of literary works is preceded by the socio-cultural life in which the author lives so that the author's attitude and outlook on life towards the problems described in his work also reflect the socio-cultural life of the community (Chatman in Nurgiyantoro, 1998: 1). As in Indonesia, especially in Java, wayang is a tradition and culture that has underpinned and played a major role in shaping the character and existence of the Indonesian people, especially those with Javanese ethnicity. For this reason, bringing wayang culture to the classroom is part of efforts to develop character as well as develop Indonesian culture.

Thus, it is no less important to introduce students in the formal education path about wayang stories which are full of noble values and local wisdom which is an alternative way to support the movement of the character education strengthening program which is now being intensely promoted by all parties in the formal education pathway. Several puppet characters are symbols of real life. The character of the Punakawan is one of the characters in the Mahabharata story puppet. Various figures in the Mahabharata puppet story can of course

be used as a learning resource for students. Narimo & Wiweko (2017) stated that "Wayang values are related to social life and religious life. The value of wayang is visibly related to the value of cooperation, harmony in life, peace, concern for others, solidarity with others, with the final estuary of peace and peace of living together. All of these things can be built with the main weapon in the form of puppets which are deliberately brought into formal education classrooms.

A performance that involves many people for the success of a puppet stage can be a lesson for students to respect other parties, be compassionate, polite and foster a sense of brotherhood regardless of degree, race, and religion. Educating students to have good morals does not have to imitate values from the outside. Because the values that exist outside are not necessarily compatible with our nation, because each nation has its own culture. As stated by Budiningsih (2008: 21), "The understanding of culture as forms of psychological achievement, namely as a complex of abstract, specific, subjective, and unobserved ideas that will color the moral life of adolescents, needs to be understood by teachers and educators. moral, as the basis for developing contextual moral education programs. Therefore, it is necessary to initiate a study of the character of the Pandawa figures in the Mahabharata story which is aligned with the cultivation of character education for the Indonesian nation. This is of course to achieve an understanding of wayang culture as a form of psychological achievement, here is specifically about the character of Pandawa figures to be aligned with government programs on the cultivation of character education for the Indonesian nation. Aligning the character of the Pandawa character in the Mahabharata story with the program of strengthening the character education of the Indonesian nation specifically can be carried out specifically for formal education.

2. Research Method

This scientific article is prepared using a qualitative descriptive method with an educational psychology approach. Descriptive analysis is used to describe a study of the character of Pandawa in the Mahabharata story. The educational psychology approach is used to align the character of the Pandawa figures with the character education of the Indonesian nation in the formal education path. This is intended to understand the power of imagination and the psyche that is generated in absorbing and living the character of Pandawa characters in a series of learning activities in the formal education path. The objective stage in the form of literature review in this article starts from the study of the character of the Pandawa character in the Mahabharata story. Then proceed with a character education strengthening program which is the mandate of the Ministry of Education and Culture in the field of education of the Indonesian nation. In the final part, in the form of a narrative as qualitative descriptive analysis in this article, explains how to align the character of the Pandawa characters in the Mahabharata story with the strengthening program of character education for the Indonesian nation specifically for the formal education pathway.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. The Pandawa Characters in the Mahabharata Story

Wayang performances as a culture certainly keep a variety of unique things in them, including a gamelan instrument as an accompaniment to the performance, there are various

stories, each time there will be a different story, there are several characters, there are characters that differ from one character to another, and so on. . Specifically about the character of the wayang characters, in general, the message will be conveyed from each character with a name and characteristics of the character's character. Narimo & Wiweko (2017) stated that "The character values contained in the wayang formations in the form of make-up on the eyebrows, eyes, nose and mouth shape include: religious, honest, responsible, loving peace; friendly, wise, optimistic, communicative and democratic ". Of the many characters in wayang stories, five protagonists are very familiar in every puppet show, namely Pandawa. The Pandawa character in the Mahabharata story consists of five brothers, each of whom is given a name and character, namely Yudhistira, Bima, Arjuna, Nakula, and Sadewa.

Based on the writer's initial understanding, Yudhistira's character is very wise, has no enemies, and has rarely lied in his life. This is following Wiyono's statement (2009: 13-20) which describes Yudhistira as a subtle, polite, wise, humble, honest, forgiving character. Meanwhile, Dyna (2015) also explains the same thing that Yudhistira is very wise, has no enemies, has rarely lied in his life, has very high morals, and likes to forgive others.

Then for the character, Bima based on the writer's understanding is a figure who is brave, has a strong physique, and still has a good heart. It is also mentioned by Wiyono (2009: 13-20) that Bima is firm, honest, fair, and indiscriminate. Then, Dyna (2015) also describes the figure of Bima as a very strong person, has long arms, is tall, has the fiercest face among his siblings, and still has a kind heart. Apart from all that, the Bima character in the puppet show is also very synonymous with a weapon called a mace.

The next character of the Pandawa is Arjuna who has a clever character, clever, conscientious, careful, polite, polite and likes to protect the weak. In this case, Wiyono (2009: 13-20) explains that the Arjuna character is clever, calm, conscientious, polite, brave, a weak protector. Dyna (2015) also mentions that Arjuna's character is charming, gentle-minded, likes to travel, study and study. Then for Nakula, it is told as the most handsome and beautiful person, a figure who works diligently and diligently respects and serves his older siblings at the same time. Wiyono (2009: 13-20) describes Nakula as an honest, loyal, obedient, compassionate, reciprocal, and trustworthy character. Likewise, Sadewa who is the twin sister of Nakula is said to have a very diligent, wise character, has advantages in the field of astronomy, and is very good at keeping secrets.

3.2. Indonesian National Character Education Strengthening Program

In general, a character can be understood as a character, personality, self-identity, identity. Character is the identity, personality, and character inherent in a person related to the psychological and physical dimensions. Ghufon (2010) describes that the micro-order character is (i) the quality and quantity of reactions to oneself, others, and certain situations, and (ii) character, morals, and psychological characteristics. The psychological characteristics possessed by individuals in the personal sphere will evolutive develop more broadly into social characteristics. Individual psychological characteristics will give color and style to group identity, which is a macro setting that will become a psychological characteristic or national character. The character building of a nation processes dynamically as a socio-ecological phenomenon.

The character of the nation is an accumulation of the characteristics of the citizens of that nation. Character is the basic value of behavior which is used as a reference for the value of human interaction, which is when the character is lost then everything is lost. Universally character is formulated as the value of living together based on the pillars: peace, respect, cooperation, freedom, happiness, honesty, humility, affection (love), responsibility, simplicity, tolerance, and unity (Gufon, 2010).

Overall, the character education of the Indonesian nation is narrowed into three important points, namely: main values, dimensions, and scope. The main values in character education are shown in Figure 1. The dimensions in character education are shown in Figure 2. And the scope for character education is shown in Figure 3. The three pictures about character education for the Indonesian nation below are accompanied by a description of the image showing a clear direction of planting character education in the formal education environment.

Figure 1. Five Main Values in Character Education

The five main values in character education that are part of the mandate are as follows.

1. Religious, is the basis for the formation of character education because, without the inculcation of religious values, character education will not be formed. A good understanding of religious values will generally be able to instill a patient, not arrogant, and not the arrogant attitude towards others. Understanding religious values will also make people love and respect each other in every activity.
2. Integrity, which means always trying to make himself a person who can be trusted in words and actions. Students with integrity will be careful in socializing because the trust given to them by their friends is very, very expensive. With the rampant practice of bullying and bullying, schools need to make a firm policy that students in schools must say and act positively between friends as part of the habit of training integrity characters.
3. Independent, which means not depending on other people to use energy, thoughts, and time to realize hopes, dreams, and ideals. Independence is closely related to one's success. In general, people who have lived independently since childhood will be

successful when they reach adulthood. That is the reason for being independent to be the leading character that children must-have in school.

4. Nationalist, means placing the interests of the nation and the state above personal and group interests. To cultivate a nationalist spirit in schools, it is necessary to start with simple things, such as students following the flag ceremony solemnly, students carrying out class cleaning tasks according to the agreement of one class, and students obeying all school regulations.
5. Cooperation, reflects the act of appreciating cooperation and working hand in hand to solve common problems. Whether we realize it or not, the tradition of cooperation is increasingly being lost due to the flow of technology that allows anyone to complete their work. This must be decided, one of which is through habituation at school such as community service, promoting deliberation, and mutual respect.

Figure 2. Dimensions in Character Education

Based on Figure 2 about the dimensions in character education, it can be understood that the movement to strengthen character education as the foundation and main spirit of education is specifically divided into four dimensions, namely: ethics, literacy, aesthetics, and kinesthetic. Characteristics of ethical character are shown by the individual spirit who has deep spirituality, faith, and piety. Characteristics of literacy characters are indicated by individual spirits who have academic excellence as a result of lifelong learning and learning processes. The characteristics of aesthetic characters are shown by the individual spirit that has moral integrity, a sense of art, and has a culture. And the characteristics of the kinesthetic character are shown by the spirit of an individual who is healthy and able to participate actively as a citizen.

Figure 3. Scope of Character Education

Based on Figure 3 about the scope of character education, it can be understood that the movement to strengthen character education is the foundation and main spirit of education which is specifically divided into four scopes, namely: an exercise of the heart thought, feeling, and sports. The scope of heart exercise includes personal characteristics who are faithful, cautious, honest, trustworthy, fair, responsible, empathetic, dare to take risks, never give up, are willing to sacrifice, and have a patriotic spirit. The scope of thinking includes personal characteristics who are intelligent, critical, creative, innovative, curious, open-minded, productive, science-oriented, and reflective. The scope of taste includes personal characteristics that are friendly, respectful, tolerant, caring, helpful, cooperative, nationalist, cosmopolitan, prioritizing public interests, proud to use Indonesian language and products, dynamic, hard work, and a work ethic. The scope of the exercise includes personal characteristics that are clean, healthy, disciplined, sportsmanship, tough, reliable, resilient, friendly, cooperative, determinative, competitive, cheerful, and persistent.

3.3. Aligning the Pandawa Characters in the Mahabharata Story with the Strengthening Indonesian National Character Education Program

When we present news of the endless chaos of this nation's life, whether through television, internet, newspapers, or other mass media, we may agree that this situation is more due to the lack of character education for the nation's children. . Educational institutions that should be on the spearhead as guardians of character toughness, often even display a figure that more reflects the lack of character status. The leakage of national exam questions in various parts of the country, the efforts of teachers and students to take all means as long as they pass, the plagiarism case that has just opened its eyes has befallen professors and doctors from well-known universities in this country, and various other cases seem to strengthen the conjecture. This is not to mention the various cases that have now befallen white-collar actors such as tax brokering and banking crimes. This situation all shows how urgent character education is to become a national issue.

How to introduce puppet culture to students in the formal education path can be in various ways, including reading wayang books, inviting to watch performances, coming to the puppet museum, the teacher bringing wayang in class, or the teacher telling stories about puppetry. Conventional methods like that can be done but sometimes need to innovate more attractive and interesting methods that can even hone children's imagination and creativity. Some parties have tried ways to make wayang acceptable and close to children, including opening a puppeteer studio for children, puppet performances by child puppeteers, making comics, animated films, puppets in tokusatsu films, and so on. etc.

The use of instructional media can generate new desires and interests, increase motivation and stimulation of learning activities, and even have a psychological effect on students. To realize ideas in the form of work, media is needed. The media problem is a formal material problem that is textual with its determination in the selection of materials, use of tools, processing techniques, approaches, and matters related to sensory absorption, following the context of its purpose. Media plays a role or has a position as a means for someone to express themselves (Djamarah, 2006: 120). The world of art education can be used as a learning medium to create a learning process that can place a working medium so important.

People certainly agree that there are many ways and "materials" that can be created to educate, cultivate and develop, and shape the character of students. The method referred to is the process and strategy, while the "materials" are teaching materials (read: subjects, subjects) that can be loaded with character education efforts. Character education in character-building efforts is not taught independently as a teaching material as is the case with other subjects, but is included and included in the learning of various subjects both in the learning process and strategy and, if possible, also inclusive in teaching materials. So, he can enter into the study of religion, art, language and literature, history, and others.

Nowadays, especially among young appreciators, in this case, children of elementary school age, wayang is not widely known. Never mind the story, they rarely know the puppet characters. Even though we can use this puppet story as a medium to educate children's characters. Wayang stories can teach humans to live in harmony, harmony, and happiness. In the puppets, examples of good and evil behavior are shown, but in the end, evil behavior will be defeated by good. By telling stories or storytelling, puppets shape ideas, morality, and behavior from generation to generation. In addition, puppets provide wholesome entertainment for the audience. There are elements of tragedy, comedy, and tragedy.

Aligning the character of the Pandawa character in the Mahabharata story with the strengthening program for the character education of the Indonesian nation specifically for the formal education pathway can be seen by the accumulation of an overall understanding of the character of the Pandawa character. In the Mahabharata story, Yudhishtira is very wise, has no enemies, and has rarely lied in his life. Then, Bima is a brave character, has a strong physique, still has a good heart, and considers everyone to be equal. As for Arjuna, he has a character who is clever, clever, conscientious, careful, polite, polite, and likes to protect the weak. And Nakula has the most handsome and handsome character, a figure who works diligently and diligently respects and serves her older siblings. Sadewa has a very diligent character, wise, has advantages in the field of astronomy, and is very good at keeping secrets.

The overall character of the Pandawa characters in the Mahabharata story falls into five main values, namely: religion, integrity, independence, nationalism, and cooperation. The

overall character of the Pandawa characters in the Mahabharata story falls into four dimensions, namely: ethics, literacy, aesthetics, and kinesthetic. Then also the overall character of the Pandawa character in the Mahabharata story falls into four scopes, namely: heart exercise thought, feeling, and exercise. Aligning the character of the Pandawa character in the Mahabharata story in a formal education environment must start from the role of the teacher, the role model of the lecturer, the role model of the leader, the role model of the character who appears in front. Then proceed with ideas and initiatives from the teacher. Ideas and initiatives from lecturers, ideas and initiatives from leaders, ideas and initiatives from all influential figures. And finally in the form of encouragement and direction from the teacher, encouragement, and direction from the lecturer, encouragement, and direction from the leader, encouragement, and direction from all influential figures. This is of course in line with the concept of Indonesian education according to Ki Hajar Dewantara, namely: ING NGARSA SUNG TULADHA which means: in the future, someone must be able to set an example or example, ING MADYA MANGUN KARSA which means: in the middle or between someone can create initiatives and ideas, and TUT WURI HANDAYANI which means: from behind an educator must be able to provide encouragement and direction.

4. Conclusion

By introducing the Mahabharata story informal learning activities, it is hoped that it can become an effort for educators to invite students or children to participate in their own culture so that it continues. The conceptual substance of this article is in the form of an effort to optimize character education through understanding the Pandawa characters in the Mahabharata story so that it can form the younger generation as human resources who have superior competencies as well as holistic characteristics as a manifestation of building the civilization of the life of the nation and state of Indonesia. And the conclusion is that harmonizing the character of the Pandawa character in the Mahabharata story in the formal education environment must be in line with the concept of Indonesian education according to Ki Hajar Dewantara, namely: ING NGARSA SUNG TULADHA which means: in the future, one must be able to set an example, ING MADYA MANGUN KARSA which means: in the middle or between someone can create initiatives and ideas, and TUT WURI HANDAYANI which means: from behind an educator must be able to provide encouragement and direction.

References

- Budiningsih, C. A. (2008). *Pembelajaran Moral Berpijak Pada Karakteristik Siswa Dan Budayanya*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Djamarah, S. B. (2006). *Strategi Belajar Mengajar*. Bandung: Sinar Baru.
- Dyna, A. (2015). Mengenal Lagi Budaya Indonesia, Tokoh Wayang Pandawa Lima. <https://www.kompasiana.com/adynpoe/54ff5e82a33311b14b50fdc2/mengenal-lagi-budaya-indonesia-tokoh-wayang-pandawa-lima>
- Ghufron, A. (2010). Integrasi Nilai-nilai Karakter Bangsa pada Kegiatan Pembelajaran. *Cakrawala Pendidikan, Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan*, Th.XXIX: 13–24.
- Haryadi, T., Irfansyah, & Santosa, I. (2013). Perancangan Visualisasi Tokoh Wayang Bambang Tetuka. *Techno.Com*, 12(1): 51–64.

- Hasani, N. I. (2013). *Pengembangan Multimedia Pembelajaran Bahasa Jawa Mengenai Tokoh Wayang Pandawa Lima untuk Siswa Sekolah Dasar*. Surakarta: Program Pascasarjana Universitas Sebelas Maret.
- Koesoemadinata, M. I. P. (2013). Wayang Kulit Cirebon: Warisan Diplomasi Seni Budaya Nusantara. *ITB J. Vis. Art & Des*, 4(2): 142–154.
- Marsaid. (2016). Islam dan Kebudayaan: Wayang Sebagai Media Pendidikan Islam di Nusantara. *Kontemplasi*, 04 (01): 101–130.
- Narimo, S. & Wiweko, A. (2017). Nilai-nilai Pendidikan Karakter dalam Tata Rias Wajah Punakawan Wayang Orang Sriwedari Surakarta. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ilmu Sosial*, 27(1): 41–48.
- Nurgiyantoro, B. (1998). *Teori Pengkajian Fiksi*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- Nurgiyantoro, B. (2011) Wayang dan Pengembangan Karakter Bangsa. *Jurnal Pendidikan Karakter*, I(1): 18–34.
- Riyanto, B. (2011). Wayang Purwa dan Tantangan Teknologi Media Baru. *Jurnal Desain Komunikasi Visual Nirmana*, 13(1): 5–11.
- Saptodewo, F. (2014). Perancangan Visualisasi Tokoh Wayang Bambang Tetuka. *Jurnal Desain*, 1(2): 102–109.
- Sulaksono, D. (2013). Filosofi Pertunjukan Wayang Purwa, *ibda' Jurnal Kebudayaan Islam*, 11(2): 238–246.
- Udasworo, W. (1999). Perancangan Visualisasi Tokoh Wayang Bambang Tetuka. *Humaniora*, 12: 38–48.
- Wiyono, K. M. (2009). *Mengenal Pandawa dan Kurawa*. Semarang: Aneka Ilmu.